

INDUSTRIAL WASTES CONTAINING GYPSUM COMPOUNDS

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Abstract. In this article, industrial waste containing gypsum compounds; Production technologies and chemical composition of phosphogypsum, borogypsum, fluorogypsum, ferrogypsum, titanogypsum, sulfogypsum, citrogypsum, hydrolysis gypsum were considered.

Keywords. Mineral, organic, gypsum, waste, orthophosphorus, fertilizer, acid, crystal.

Industrial waste, which can be used as a raw material for the production of gypsum binders, is generated in various enterprises that produce mineral or organic substances. To date, there are approximately 50 types of waste containing gypsum. A large amount of phosphogypsum, which is waste from the production of superphosphates, has been accumulated in the republic. Such waste is produced in large quantities at the Almalyk and Samarkand chemical plants. Phosphogypsum waste has reached 25 million tons and is increasing by 3-4 million tons every year.

Yu. According to the proposal of G. Mesheryakov, waste can be divided into the following classes according to their origin:

- in the process of obtaining mineral acids: phosphogypsum and phosphohemihydrate in the production of orthophosphoric acid, borogypsum in the production of orthoboric acid, and hydrofluoric acid is a by-product of the production of plavic acid; organic acids: citrogypsum and tartrate gypsum are side products of production of citric and tartaric acids;
- in chemical processing of wood - hydrolysis gypsum;
- gypsum, which belongs to the group of complex sulfates, in the production of complex fertilizers from minerals and rocks;
- as a result of treatment with aqueous solutions of salts - silica gypsum ΓeSO_4 ;
- in the process of cleaning industrial gases containing SO_3 - sulfur gypsum;
- as a result of processing aqueous solutions of acids formed during the process of obtaining TiO_2 - titanogypsum;
- in the extraction of salts from lake, sea and ocean waters - saline gypsum;
- in the synthesis of vitamins - vitamin gypsum.

Phosphogypsum is a mineral fertilizer production waste, and according to its composition, it is divided into apatite and phosphorite phosphogypsum. During the decomposition of phosphates with sulfuric acid, waste can also be released in the production of phosphoric acid. In this case, as a result of phosphoric acid entering the solution, calcium sulfate (phosphogypsum) is formed:

In this case, depending on the adopted technology, semi-aqueous gypsum or anhydrite can be precipitated instead of calcium sulfate dihydrate. Gypsum containing 80-98% calcium sulfate dihydrate can be used as a raw material for gypsum binder. High dispersion of the material $S_{\text{sol.}} = 350\text{-}380 \text{ m}^2 / \text{kg}$ allows to exclude the grinding operation from the technological process. Humidity up to

40% complicates the process of its preparation and requires a lot of fuel for drying. The presence of phosphate compounds negatively affects the quality of gypsum binder. They can slow down the bite and reduce the strength of the finished product.

Borogypsum is a waste product of boric acid and boron production. It is obtained by breaking down natural borates with the help of sulfuric acid, separating their liquid and solid phases. The amount of gypsum in waste is 77-83%. It is a third- or fourth-grade raw material, and the product obtained as a result of the decomposition of borates with a high content of boron oxide can contain up to 94% gypsum dihydrate. On average, about 76% is $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and up to 21% is SiO_2 . The humidity of the clay is up to 45%. The main impurities are amorphous silica and boric acid. First, it reduces the quality of gypsum binders due to the increased demand for water. The latter slows down the hydration of semi-aqueous gypsum and reduces its water content, which leads to an increase in the compressive strength of the artificial stone and a decrease in the bending strength.

Fluorogypsum is a waste product of the production of sulfuric acid from fluorides, which can be roughly described by the following equation.

The composition is up to 70% anhydrite, 20% calcium sulfate dihydrate and 2% fluorite. The acidity index of the raw material does not exceed pN 2, therefore it is necessary to neutralize it when obtaining a gypsum binder. Metal equipment used for waste treatment can be corroded by hydrofluoric acid residues (Table 1.2).

**Waste containing sulfate compounds
chemical composition, %**

Waste	Ca	SO ₃	H ₂	SiO	Al ₂ O ₃	R ₂	R ₂ O ₅	CaS
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					O ₃				
Phosphogyps um	31,7 0	45,1 0	20,0 0	0,90	0,90	0,2 0	1,30	0,60	95,60
Fluorogyps m	38,6 0	52,5 0	3,70	2,00	0,50	0,2 0	0,02	–	97,40
Borogypsum	25,4 0	35,2 0	16,0 0	20,8 0	1,80	1,1 0	–	–	76,70

Ferrogypsum is obtained by treating iron sulfate solution with milk of lime. As a result of the processing of saline solutions of electrical engineering steel, a clay containing 35-40% CaSO₄ 2H₂O, 6-7% SiO₂ and up to 50% liquid phase is formed. After processing with milk of lime, the amount of dihydrate increases to 68-70% and SiO₂ to 6-7%. Due to the presence of silicon oxide, it is sometimes called silicon gypsum. Due to the presence of a large number of impurities, it is considered a low-quality raw material.

Titanogypsum is a waste product of processing titanium raw materials, usually ilmenite, with sulfuric acid. Titanium dioxide is obtained by decomposing ores with sulfuric acid. 7-8 tons of liquid phase containing sulfuric acid corresponds to 1 t of TiO₂. The cleaning of the liquid phase is carried out by neutralization using milk of lime, which leads to the formation of a sludge consisting of gypsum crystals that are difficult to dissolve in water, mixtures and the liquid phase. Titanogypsum contains up to 88% CaSO₄ 2H₂O; 5–6% SaSO₃; It can be 1-2% Al₂O₃ and others.

Sulfogypsum is a product for cleaning industrial gases of solid fuel thermal power plants from SO₃–. Purification is carried out with lime, and as a result, SaSO₄ is formed. It is oxidized by oxygen in reactors and a characteristic light

gray material is formed, consisting mainly of gypsum crystals, with a relative surface area of 280–300 m²/kg and a moisture content of 28–30%. Composition of calcium sulfate dihydrate

It is 93-95%, which meets the requirements of I-grade raw materials. The amount of unwanted impurities is represented by 1.6-1.7% calcium carbonates, 0.03% fluorite, up to 3% inert substances in the form of dust or ash. The pH value of the aqueous solution of sulfur gypsum is 4.5-9. The dry bulk density is 520-530 kg / m³, and the actual density is -2350-2370 kg / m³.

Citrogypsum is a waste product from the production of citric acid. The separation of citric acid crystals is based on the low solubility of its calcium salts in water. As a result, the acid turns into tricalcium citrate, which is difficult to dissolve.

The washed calcium citrate decomposes under the influence of sulfuric acid

Citric acid solution is separated from gypsum, calcium oxalate and berlin blue in tape vacuum filters. The solution is evaporated and crystallized, and the dried waste with a moisture content of 60% is sent to the landfill. Chemical composition of citrogypsum, % by mass: CaO 29.7–32.6; SO₃ 38.3–45.5; SiO₂ 0.2–1.7; R₂O₃ 0.3–1.2; MgO 0.1-0.4; Δ_{mp} = 22.0–28.4. Density 2030–2470 kg/m³; specific surface area 490–780 m²/kg, gypsum dihydrate content 83–97%. Depending on the production method, these wastes can be of 1-4 types.

Tartratogypsum is a waste product of tartaric acid production and contains 62-64% calcium dihydrate.

Vitamin plaster is produced as a result of vitamin A production. It may contain mixtures of methanol and acetone. According to the Department of Building Materials, Products and Constructions of the Belgorod State

Technological University, the resulting clay consists of 95-98% calcium sulfate dihydrate and consists of 50-120 μm thin layer $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals.

Hydrolysis gypsum is a waste product of cellulose processing. Alcohol, turpentine, furfural, yeast, carbon dioxide and a number of other technical products are obtained during the hydrolysis of plant stems diluted with sulfuric acid. Milk of lime is added to neutralize sulfuric acid. As a result, a precipitate consisting of semi-hydrated gypsum is formed. At a temperature of 85 ° C, it turns into a stable dihydrate, but due to the presence of lignin, dextrin, furfurol, xylan residues, sulfuric acid salts and other technical impurities, organic impurities are adsorbed on the surface of its crystals and adversely affect the technical properties of gypsum binders obtained from it, in particular , slows down hydration and reduces the strength of hardened plaster.

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